

The Implementation of the Cotton Monopoly Policy in the Surkhandarya Oasis in 1946-1970 and its Results

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Abstract: In the years after World War II, large irrigation facilities began to be built in Uzbekistan. This process was carried out in accordance with the orders of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) and the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR issued in July 1945 and February 2, 1946. The period of construction of large irrigation networks has begun in Surkhandarya region.

Keywords: Surkhan-Sherabad, Khazarbag, Tallimaran, the Council of Ministers of the USSR, the new lands in the Surkhandarya basin were transferred to the "South Surkhan Reservoir."

Agriculture in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis was associated with the reconstruction of irrigation systems in the Sherabad River and the Zang Canal. The development of new lands was primarily carried out at the expense of collective farms. In 1949, collective farmers from the Jarkurgan and Termez districts constructed the Kakaydi Canal with a length of 23 km, and in 1956, the Zang Canal with a length of 90 km. The Yangarik canal in Termez district was renovated, and the Aktepa massif on the left bank of the Surkhandarya River was developed. At the same time, the Shaldyrak, Akkurgan, and Aktepin marshes in the Shurchinsky district, the Kampirkul marshes in the Denau district, the Akkurgan, Garangtukay, and Zarkamar Turkmenshlak, Jaloyir, and Kumkurgan marshes in the Jarkurgan district, and the Jartekis and Fayzabad marshes in the Sariasiy district were developed. Due to newly developed lands, cotton yields reached 14.8 centners in 1946, and 25.9 centners in 1953. The area of fine-fiber cotton has increased tenfold.

Through the efforts of the workers of Sherabad and Baysun districts, the Mirshodi steppe in the Shurchin district was developed. The next line of the Khazarbag canal was built to carry water to the newly opened massif. As a result, some parts of Sherabad and Boysun districts were provided with water. In September 1949, by order of the government, water was pumped from the Zang Canal into the Tallimaron massif and the development of the desert began. The Chulkuvar expedited the excavation and drainage of the 18-kilometer Tallimaron canal. After 90 days, the canal was completed by manual excavation.

In 1950, significant work was carried out in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis to transition to a new irrigation system, expand irrigated areas, save water, and prevent soil salinization with the goal of introducing comprehensive mechanization into agricultural production. Between 1951 and 1952, workers from the Jarkurgan, Termez, Angor, Sherabad, and Shurchi districts conducted extensive work on cleaning and expanding the Zang Canal, improving the water supply of arable land. As a result of the measures taken, agricultural land expanded to 155.2 thousand hectares in 1950, of which 59.7 thousand hectares were cotton fields.

The characteristic of irrigation and land reclamation measures in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis in the postwar period was that, firstly, measures were taken to ensure the best conditions for water

management in existing systems. Secondly, irrigated lands and lands were developed and introduced into the agricultural sector. However, the lack of water resources did not allow the oasis to provide agriculture with water. This problem could be solved only through the efficient use of Surkhandarya water. To do this, it was necessary to build new irrigation canals from the Surkhandarya River, collect spring and winter water flowing into the Amu Darya River, and use it for the benefit of the national economy.

To solve the aforementioned problem, on September 2, 1952, the Council of Ministers of the USSR adopted a special resolution on the construction of the Uchkyzyl Reservoir with a capacity of 165 million cubic meters and the opening of 10,000 hectares of new land in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis for the purpose of developing new lands. In order to strengthen the cotton monopoly, the Soviet government paid special attention to the water supply of collective farms, allocated 48 million soums for the Uchkyzyl reservoir in Surkhandarya region and the Tuyabuguz reservoir in Tashkent region, and took control of the acceleration of these reservoirs. He also gave instructions on the extension and reconstruction of the Zang canal. A special inter-collective farm council consisting of 27 people was formed to implement this decision. The total volume of land works carried out along the Zang canal was 400,000 m³, and 300,000 m³ of work was completed to reconstruct the entire collective farm's irrigation and collector system. 2.5 million soums were allocated for the implementation of these works. Significant attention was paid to the use of mechanization for the development of the Surkhan-Sherabad region, the construction of new irrigation systems, and the commissioning of collector-drainage systems. In 1953, 6,000 tractors and 2,200 automobiles were involved in the oasis's agriculture. In order to expand cotton fields in the oasis and provide them with constant water, on February 3, 1961, the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR adopted a resolution "On measures for the development and irrigation of new lands in the Surkhandarya basin by the force of the "South Surkhandarya Reservoir." According to it, the issue of development of 86.3 thousand hectares of land in seven years, as well as the introduction of 35 thousand hectares of new lands in the "Zang" system into agricultural turnover was considered.

To develop new lands at the expense of the South Surkhan Reservoir, the Surkhandarya Agricultural Trust was established in 1961. Thus, the large-scale development of the Sherabad steppe began on the basis of the South Surkhan Reservoir. The South Surkhan Reservoir with a capacity of 800 million cubic meters was built on the lands of the "VLKSM 30 yilligi" state farm in the Shurchinsky district, on the site of riparian forests between Zarkamar and Khodjamulki. The design of the reservoir began in 1958, and the main construction work began in 1961. The maximum height of the dam is 30 meters, the width of the upper part is 10 meters, the length along the edge is 5.4 km. The total surface area of the reservoir is 65 km². Its task was to regulate the seasonal flow of the Surkhan River and use it for the needs of the national economy. The reservoir collected spring floodwaters and created the possibility of irrigating 71,000 hectares of land in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis through the Sherabad and Kumkurgan main canals during the dry summer season. Since 1962, the South Surkhan Reservoir has been providing the oasis's agriculture with the necessary water source. Six years later, in 1968, the reservoir was fully operational.

In the 1960s, 70 excavators, 20 scrapers, 120 bulldozers, 210 trucks, 80 tractors, and other equipment were involved in the development of new lands, construction, and reconstruction of irrigation systems in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis. As a result of the measures taken in 1964, 3660 hectares of new lands were developed in the Sherabad Steppe according to the Zang system, and 1020 hectares were planted with cotton. The necessary technical means have been delivered for construction organizations developing virgin lands. For example, in 1963, the construction trust No. 11 had 13 excavators in the reserve, while in 1964 their number reached 50. The number of cars and cranes increased from 5 to 23 per year.

In order to develop new lands in the Surkhandarya region, the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR on July 7, 1965, assigned the task of "Uzglavvodstroy" to focus on improving the irrigation and reclamation condition of the state farms in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis. As a result, in 1966

the Zang Canal was completely reconstructed or pumped 5 times more water than the capacity at the time of construction. In the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, "Uzglavvodstroy" improved the irrigation and reclamation condition of 4.1 thousand hectares of land in 1966, 9 thousand hectares in 1967, 11 thousand hectares in 1968, 12.6 thousand hectares in 1969, and 14.0 thousand hectares in 1970. In 1965, cotton was sown on 3,635 hectares in Yangiabad, 4,000 hectares in Komsomolobod, and 2,100 hectares in Sovetabad. In 1965, the area of agricultural crops in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis increased from 166.6 thousand hectares to 214.8 thousand hectares.

In 1966, on the basis of the Irrigation and Development Program of the Sherabad Steppe, the development of the Yangi Istara and Kizirik masses, which are the oldest fertile lands of the Sherabad oasis, began. This work was related to the construction of the South Surkhan Reservoir and the Sherabad Machine Main Canal. The Sherabad Main Canal, 27 kilometers long, receives water from the main water intake structure built on the right bank of the South Surkhan Reservoir. During the first 8 kilometers of the canal's route, the trickling water flows along the right bank of the Surkhandarya River and under the Tashkupriksay channel, passing through a 150-meter (3-x3.5 m) long iron-concrete pipeline dock. Below, a discharge device was installed to discharge 10 m³/sec of water from the canal into the Kumkurgan canal. A Sherabad pumping station was built on the 13 km section of the canal. There, with the help of powerful pumps-aggregates, water is pumped to the height of a 10-story building. In 1966, the Sherabad Main Canal first supplied water to the Kyzyrakdara Steppe. Five years later, in 1971, the Sherabad Main Canal was fully commissioned. The Sherabad Main Canal is divided into right and left branches on a 27-kilometer section. The length of the left branch of the canal is 29.6 km, and the channel is covered with concrete pavement. This is crucial for reducing water consumption. Water permeability is 25 m³/sec. The length of the right channel is 76.6 km and serves to irrigate the lands of the Sherabad-Darya system. It was also covered with a concrete floor.

Along with the construction of the reservoir and the main canal, a large-scale irrigation and collector-drainage system was built. As a result of 10 years of work, 1047 km of concrete and reinforced concrete irrigation canals, 936 km of open collectors, and 1690 km of horizontal drainage were constructed for the development of the desert. The solution of the water issue allowed for the development of 2,000 hectares of virgin land in 1962, and 8,000 hectares in 1963. By the end of 1972, 60,000 hectares of land had been put into operation.

In 1968, with the construction of the left branch of the canal, two reserve collective farms were established on the new lands of the Bandikhan-Kyzyrik massif. In 1968, 3,238 hectares of virgin lands were developed, of which 1,000 hectares were cotton-planted. In 1968, the 7th state farm named after Y. Akhunbabaev was established on the Sherabad Machine Main Canal system, 2,100 hectares of new land were developed, and 400 hectares of land were planted with cotton. That year, 538 tons of cotton were handed over to the state, and 13 centners of cotton were harvested from each hectare. Until 1972, 8 cotton farms were established on the territory of the Sherabad Main Canal. In 1968, state farms in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis delivered 28,346 tons of cotton to the state. Between 1958 and 1968, cotton fields in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis increased from 82,451 hectares to 111,500 hectares. If in 1958, 236,000 tons of cotton were delivered to the state in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, then by 1968 this figure reached 346,300 tons.

As a result of the work carried out at the "South Surkhan Reservoir" complex, sufficient water was collected in the south of the region for irrigation at any time of the year. Agrotechnical methods developed over centuries have been critically reviewed, adapting them to conditions of low water availability. The time has come to more fully utilize the material and technical, as well as natural and climatic conditions of the developed valley.

After the completion of irrigation and land reclamation works, the amount of irrigated land in the south of the region was increased to 180,000 hectares, which is significantly more than in all districts of the region. By 1969, more than 90 percent of the region's total irrigated land was

irrigated by water accumulated in reservoirs. When land is irrigated from natural sources of water, a lot of silt flows into it along with water. These silt deposits are one of the factors that preserve and restore the natural fertility of the land.

The creation of new state farms in Surxondaryo Region is directly linked to the implementation of large-scale irrigation projects and the development of virgin lands in the Sherabad Steppe. Nuriddin Murodov (1915-1974), who served as the first secretary of the Surkhandarya Regional Party Committee from 1965 to 1974, made a significant contribution to this work. N. Murodov was active in developing the productive forces of Surxondaryo Region, especially in cotton growing and horticulture. He made a worthy contribution to the creation of new districts and cities in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis. N. Murodov was awarded the title of Hero of Socialist Labor for his great achievements in the development of cotton growing, the widespread use of scientific achievements and best practices in production, and obtaining high yields.

In addition, the work of Heroes of Labor - Shaimardon Kudratov, Otamurod Khudoynazarov, Jiyankul Rustamov, Muhammadi Keldiyev, Boboyor Khasanov, and others, honored cotton growers of the republic - Nazirtosh Turaev, Sayidjon Otaniyozov, Aliqul Fayziev, Rahima Abdurakhmanova, Kumri Kurbanova, Norqobil Akhmedov, Kuchar Odinaev, and others is of particular importance in the development of new lands and cotton growing in

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